

Codebook

Open questions:

Associations based on the effects of images

(3 columns, one code per column for each answer, the first three answers were included in the evaluation, i.e., up to three codes per participant)

a) Image ‘barn office’

Category	Code	Examples
Terms of digital transformation	1	Digitalization, technology, data
Type of workplace	2	Office job, office, work, modern office, home office
Characteristics of the workplace	3	Neat, tidy, clear, computer skills are very important, structured
Positive or neutral connotations	4	Modern, progress, efficiency, knowledge, innovation, future, meaningful
Negative connotations	5	Complicated, reduced animal contact, costs, only numbers, technical issues,
Benefits	6	Management, control, estrus detection, (animal) monitoring, time savings, animal welfare, (improving) animal health
Others	7	Program interface, feed intake, milk yield, well known, hygiene

b) Image ‘calf rail’

Category	Code	Examples
Negative connotations	1	Unnatural, impersonal, alienation, animal health? animal welfare? Lack of control, inadequate control, industry, factory farming
Positive connotations	2	Labor saving, adequate feeding, good supply, work facilitation, efficient, innovation, hygiene
Terms of digital transformation	3	Automation, technology, digitalization, calf feeder
Disadvantages for calves	4	Lack of contact to dam, lonely, lack of human contact, isolation
Others	5	Black, medicines via feeding, milk substitute, calf, milk

Do you consider yourself adequately prepared for the digital transformation in dairy farming as a result of your college education?

Category	Code	Examples or specific criteria
No statement	0	Answer field empty, no answer
Yes	1	Yes, certainly, mostly
No	2	No, not at all, rather not, -
Probably not	3	Probably not
Partially	4	Rather moderate, moderate, partially, more or less, in part, yes and no
Do not know	5	Not yet foreseeable, I don't know, no idea, ?, I'm unable to assess it, I hope, I can only hope so